

Generalization of a fixed point theorem of Suzuki type in complete metric space

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to generalize a fixed point result given by Popescu[17]. Our results complement and extend very recent results proved by Suzuki [T. Suzuki, A generalized Banach contraction principle that characterizes metric completeness, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 136 (2008) 1861 - 1869]. To validate our result an example is given.

Key Words and Phrases: Common fixed point; Complete metric Space.

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1. Introduction

Let (X, d) be a metric space, T a self-mapping on X and k a nonnegative real number such that the inequality $d(Tx, Ty) \leq kd(x, y)$ holds for any $x, y \in X$. If $k < 1$ then T is said to be a contractive mapping and if $k = 1$, then T is said to be a nonexpansive mapping. The Banach theorem states that if X is complete, then every contractive mapping has a unique fixed point. There exists a vast literature about contractive and nonexpansive type mappings, where the contractive and nonexpansive conditions are substituted with more general conditions (see, for instance [1 - 10]).

Bogin[1] proved the following result.

Theorem 1.1. Let (X, d) be a nonempty complete metric space and $T : X \rightarrow X$ a mapping satisfying

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq ad(x, y) + b[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)] + c[d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)], \quad (1)$$

here $a \geq 0$, $b > 0$, $c > 0$ and $a + 2b + 2c = 1$. Then T has a unique fixed point.

This result was generalized by Li[15] and Gregus[11] considered a class of self-mapping T on X which satisfy (1) with $c = 0$. He proved the following theorem.

Theorem 1.2 Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $S : X \rightarrow X$. Define a non-increasing function θ from $[0, 1)$ onto $(1/2, 1]$ by

$$\theta(r) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 0 \leq r \leq \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}; \\ \frac{r-1}{r^2}, & \text{if } \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2} \leq r \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}; \\ \frac{1}{1+r}, & \text{if } \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \leq r \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

Assume that there exists $r \in [0, 1)$ such that $\theta(r)d(x, Sx) \leq d(x, y)$ implies

$d(Sx, Sy) \leq rd(x, y)$, for all $x, y \in X$. Then S has a unique fixed point. Also, Kikkawa and Suzuki[14] proved Kannan, Meir and Keeler [13] versions of Theorem 1.2. Moreover, Suzuki studied a class of operators satisfying the following condition.

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Theorem 1.3 Let T be a mapping on a subset C of a Banach space E . Then T is said to satisfy condition (C) if for all $x, y \in C$

$$(C) \quad 1/2 \|Tx - Ty\| \leq \|x - y\|.$$

In 2010, Tiwari et al. [18] proved a common fixed point theorem for weakly compatible mapping in symmetric spaces satisfying an integral type contractive condition. Recently Popescu [17] proved the following theorem.

Theorem 1.4 Let (X, d) be a nonempty complete metric space and $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping satisfying $1/2 d(x, Tx) \leq d(x, y)$ implies

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq ad(x, y) + b[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)] + c[d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \quad (2)$$

where $a \geq 0, b > 0, c > 0$ and $a + 2b + 2c = 1$. Then T has a unique fixed point.

Inspired by this theorem, we present a common fixed point result of Suzuki type in complete metric space in this paper.

2. Main results

The following theorem generalizes result of Popescu[17].

Theorem 2.1. Let (X, d) be a nonempty complete metric space and $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping satisfying $\frac{1}{2}d(x, Tx) \leq d(x, y)$ implies

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, Ty) + p \max\{d(x, y), d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty), d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)\} \\ \leq ad(x, y) + b[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)] + c[d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where $a \geq 0, b > 0, c > 0, p \geq 0$ and $a + 2b + 2c - 2p = 1$. Then T has a unique fixed point.

Proof. Let $x \in X$ be arbitrary. we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, T^2x) + p \max\{d(x, Tx), [d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x)], [d(x, T^2x) + d(Tx, Tx)]\} \\ \leq a d(x, Tx) + b [d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x)] + c [d(x, T^2x) + d(Tx, Tx)]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, T^2x) + p \max\{d(x, Tx), d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x), d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x)\} \\ \leq (a + b)d(x, Tx) + b d(Tx, T^2x) + c [d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x)]. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, T^2x) &\leq (a+b+c-p)/(1-b-c-p) d(x, Tx) \\ &= d(x, Tx). \end{aligned}$$

This implies that the sequence $\{d_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ is a decreasing one, where

$$d_n := d(T^n x, T^{n+1} x) \quad \text{and} \quad T^0 x = x.$$

Next, we will show that there exists a nonnegative number $m < 2$ such that

$$d(Tx, T^3x) \leq md_0. \quad \text{First, we suppose that } d(x, T^2x) \geq d(x, Tx). \quad \text{Then } 1/2d(x, Tx) \leq d(x, T^2x)$$

and we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, T^3x) + p \max\{d(x, T^2x), d(x, Tx) + d(T^2x, T^3x), d(x, T^3x) + d(Tx, Tx)\} \\ \leq a d(x, T^2x) + b d(x, Tx) + b d(T^2x, T^3x) + c d(x, T^3x) + cd(Tx, T^2x). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$d(Tx, T^3x) + p \max\{d(x, Tx), d(Tx, T^3x)\} \leq a(d_0+d_1) + bd_0 + bd_2 + c[d_0 + d(Tx, T^3x)] d_1.$$

Setting $m = (1+a)/(1-c-p)$, we have $m_1 < 2$ and $d(Tx, T^3x) \leq m_1 d_0$. Now, we assume that $d(x, T^2x) < d(x, Tx)$. Since

$$d(Tx, T^2x) + p \max\{d(x, Tx), d(x, Tx) + d(Tx, T^2x), d(x, T^2x) + d(Tx, Tx)\} \\ \leq a d(x, Tx) + b d(x, Tx) + b d(Tx, T^2x) + c d(x, T^2x) + c d(Tx, Tx),$$

we get $d_1 < (a+b)d_0 + bd_1 + cd_0 + p(d_0 + d_1)$. Hence, $d_1 < (a+b+c-p) / (1-b-p)$ and then

$$d(Tx, T^3x) \leq d(Tx, T^2x) + d(T^2x, T^3x) \leq 2d(Tx, T^2x) \leq (2a + 2b + 2c - 2p)/(1-b+p) \cdot d_0 = (1+a)/(1-b+p).$$

Setting $m_2 = (1+a)/(1-b-p)$, we have, $m_2 < 2$ and $d(Tx, T^3x) \leq m_2 d_0$.

Taking $m = \max\{m_1, m_2\}$, we get $0 < m < 2$ and $d(Tx, T^3x) \leq md(x, Tx)$, for all $x \in X$.

Since $1/2 d(Tx, T^2x) \leq d(Tx, T^2x)$ we have,

$$d(T^2x, T^3x) + p \max\{d(Tx, T^2x), [d(Tx, T^2x) + d(T^2x, T^3x)], d(Tx, T^3x)\} \\ \leq a d(Tx, T^2x) + b[d(Tx, T^2x) + d(T^2x, T^3x)] + cd(Tx, T^3x).$$

Thus,

$$d_2 \leq (a + 2b - 2p)d_0 + mcd_0 = (a + 2b + 2p + mc)d_0$$

Setting $k = a + 2b - 2p + mc$, we have $k < 1$ and $d_2 \leq kd_0$ for all $x \in X$.

Let $x_0 \in X$ and $u_n = T^n x_0$. Then $d_{n+2} \leq kd_n$ for all $n \geq 0$, where $d_n = d(u_n, u_{n+1})$. Therefore, for any even integer $n \geq 0$ we have by induction $d_n \leq k^{n/2} d_0 \leq k^{(n-1)/2} d_0$ and for every odd integer $n \geq 1$ we have also by induction $d_n \leq k^{(n-1)/2} d_1 \leq k^{(n-1)/2} d_0$. Hence, for all $n \geq 0$ we get $d_n \leq k^{(n-1)/2} d_0$.

Since $k \in (0, 1)$ we obtain that u_n is a Cauchy sequence and by completeness of X there exists $z \in X$ such that the sequence $\{u_n\}$ converges to z as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Next, we will show that z is a fixed point of T . Assuming that there exists n such that

$$d(z, u_n) < 1/2d(u_n, u_{n+1}) \text{ and } d(z, u_{n+1}) < 1/2d(u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}) \text{ we obtain}$$

$$d_n = d(u_n, u_{n+1}) \leq d(z, u_n) + d(z, u_{n+1}) < 1/2(d_n + d_{n+1}) \leq d_n.$$

This is a contradiction, so for all $n \geq 0$ we have either $d(z, u_n) \geq 1/2d(u_n, u_{n+1})$ or

$$d(z, u_{n+1}) \geq 1/2d(u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}). \text{ Thus, there exists a subsequence } \{n_j\} \text{ of } n \text{ such that } d(u_{n_j}, z) \leq 1/2d(u_{n_{j+1}}, u_{n_j}) \text{ for every integer } j \geq 0. \text{ Then, we have}$$

$$d(Tz, u_{n_j+1}) + p \max\{d(z, u_{n_j}), d(z, Tz) + d(u_{n_j}, u_{n_j+1}), d(z, u_{n_j+1}) + d(Tz, u_{n_j})\} \\ \leq ad(z, u_{n_j}) + bd(z, Tz) + bd(u_{n_j}, u_{n_j+1}) + cd(z, u_{n_j+1}) + cd(Tz, u_{n_j}).$$

Taking $j \rightarrow \infty$ we get $d(Tz, z) \leq (b+c)d(Tz, z)$. This implies $d(Tz, z) = 0$ and so, $Tz = z$. If

z' is another fixed point T then $d(z', z) \leq 1/2d(z, Tz) = 0$ and then

$$d(z', z) = d(Tz', Tz) + p \max\{d(z', z), [d(z, z') + d(z, z)], [d(z', z) + d(z, z)]\} \\ \leq a d(z', z) + b [d(z, z') + d(z, z)] + c [d(z', z) + d(z, z)].$$

Hence,

$$d(z', z) \leq (a + 2c - 2p)d(z', z).$$

This implies $d(z', z) = 0$, which is a contradiction. So, T has a unique fixed point.

Remark 2.2 2 If we put $p = 0$ in above, we get Theorem 1.4 of Popescu[17].

Now we present the following example to validate our result.

Example 2.3. Let $X = [-1, 1]$ with the usual metric and let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be given as

$$Tx = \begin{cases} -x, & \text{if } x \in [0, 1/2) \cup (1/2, 1] = U; \\ \frac{x}{4}, & \text{if } x \in [-1, 0) = V; \\ 0, & \text{if } x = \frac{1}{2}. \end{cases}$$

We will prove that:

1. T has a unique fixed point.

2. T satisfies condition (3) with $a = 1/3$, $b = c = 1/4$, $p = 1/6$

i.e. $1/2 d(x, Tx) \leq d(x, y) \Rightarrow d(Tx, Ty) \leq m(x, y)$ where

$m(x, y) = 1/3 d(x, y) + 1/4 [d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty) + d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] - p \max\{d(x, y), d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty), d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)\}$.

3. T does not satisfy Suzuki condition of Theorem 1.2.

4. T does not satisfy Popescu condition of Theorem 1.4 with $a = 1/3$, $b = c = 1/4$ and $p = 1/6$.

Proof. 1 is obvious. Secondly we consider the following.

(i) For $x, y \in U$ then

$m(x, y) = 1/3 |y - x| + (1/4 + 1/4)|2y + 2x| - 1/6 |2y + 2x| = 1/3 |y - x| + 1/2 |2y + 2x| - 1/6 |2y + 2x|$, or

$m(x, y) = (1/3 |y - x| + 2/3 |y + x|) \geq |y - x| = d(Tx, Ty)$ and (2) holds.

(ii) If $x, y \in V$, then $m(x, y) = (1/3 + 3/4(1/4 + 1/4 + 1/6))|y - x| = 5/6 |y - x| \geq 1/4 |y - x| = d(Tx, Ty)$ so (2) holds.

(iii) If $x \in U, y \in V$, then $m(x, y) = 1/3 |(x - y)| + (1/4 + 1/4 + 1/6)|2x - 3y/4| = 13x/12 - 5y/24 + 1/4 |y + x| \geq x + y/4 = d(Tx, Ty)$ so (2) holds.

(iv) If $x \in V, y \in U$, then $m(x, y) \geq d(Tx, Ty)$ like in (iii).

(v) For $x \in U, y = 1/2$, then $m(x, y) = 1/3 |x - 1/2| + (1/4 |4x + 1| - 1/6 |2x|) = x + 1/12 \geq x = d(Tx, Ty)$

and (2) holds.

(vi) For $x \in V, y = 1/2$, then $m(x, y) = 1/3 |x - 1/2| + 1/4 |3x/2 + 1| - 1/6 |3x/4 + 1/2| = 7x/12 \geq x/4 = d(Tx, Ty)$ and (2) holds.

(vii) If $x = 1/2, y \in U$, then $m(x, y) = 1/3 |y - 1/2| + 1/4 |1 + 4y| - 1/6 |2y + 1/2| = y + 5/6 \geq d(Tx, Ty)$ and (2) holds.

(viii) If $x = 1/2, y \in V$, then

$m(x, y) = 1/3 |1/2 - y| + 1/4 |3y/2 + 1| - 1/12 - y/8 = 1/3 + y/6 \geq 1/2$ and $d(Tx, Ty) = 0 - y/4, -y/4 \leq 1/4 (y/4 \in [-1/4, 0))$ Hence (2) holds.

(xi) If $x = y$ then (2) is obvious.

(3) If $x = 0, y = 1$, then $\theta(r)d(x, Tx) = 0 < 1 = d(x, y)$ and $d(Tx, Ty) = 1$, so condition from Theorem 1.2. does not hold.

(4) If $x = 1/2, y = 1$ we have $d(Tx, Ty) = 1$ and $m(x, y) = 1/3 |1| + 1/4 |1/2 - 0| + 1/4 |1| = 1/3 + 1/8 + 1/4 + 1/4 = 23/24$ so $d(Tx, Ty) > m(x, y)$. Therefore Popescu's condition Theorem 1.4 does not hold.

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